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MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

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**REVIEW ON THE MANAGEMENT AND DISPOSITION OF CONFISCATED
FOREST PRODUCTS AND TURNED OVER LOGS IN DENR CENRO LIPA CITY,
BATANGAS**

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17 May 2023

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

ANGELA MARIE BROSAS AGAPAY

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Abstract

To avoid deterioration and loss of the economic value of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs, impounding areas were established. These forest products were hauled and temporarily deposited in the impounding area of DENR CENRO Lipa. This study intended to review the management and disposition of DENR CENRO Lipa with regards to confiscated forest products and turned-over logs from approved tree cutting permits issued to NGA's.

The unavailability of proper/huge storage facilities is a problem experienced by DENR CENRO Lipa in the management of forest products. Missing forest products and parts of impounded conveyances/machinery were also an issue due to lack of security in the storage facility. Weak compliance of the DPWH/NGA in the terms and conditions on the accounting of the turned-over logs was also observed.

The Department is advised should prioritize the establishment of proper storage facility based on the design and layout indicated in DMO 2023-03. A harmonized tree cutting and prompt/proper disposition policy for turned-over logs should be considered by the Department. Furthermore, it is recommended to create a Regional Council/Technical Working Group that will take responsibility and oversee the monitoring and disposition of the apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deforestation, illegal logging/timber trade, land conversion and resource overexploitation have been considered as the most critical constraints for sustainable forest management all over the world. For this purpose, Forest Law Enforcement and Governance (FLEG) is indeed the country's recognizable field of professional practice to mitigate these environmental problems and forest crimes (Pescott, M. J., & Durst, P. B., 2010).

In the Philippines, the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) is mandated as the primary government agency responsible for the conservation, management, development, and proper use of the country's environment and natural resources to ensure equitable sharing of the benefits derived from the country's natural resources for the welfare of the present and future generations of Filipinos (E.O. 192 of 1987).

Anti-Illegal Logging and Forest Protection Program

DENR has been persistent in its campaign to intensify Forest Protection and Law Enforcement within its jurisdiction. Their priority programs/activities under Forest Protection Program includes (a) Issuance of Tenurial Instrument/Management Arrangement and Permit Issuance; (b) Consistent apprehension, & mandatory administrative adjudication and confiscation of undocumented forest products including conveyances and other implements; and (c) Sustainable implementation of the Lawin Forest and Biodiversity Protection System.

Presidential Decree (PD) No. 75 or the Revised Forestry Code of 1975 became the blueprint of forest management in the Philippines. According to Section 68 of PD

705, “cutting, gathering, collecting, removing, possessing timber or other forest products from any forestland or from private land, without any legal documents/license shall be punished with penalties imposed under Articles 309 and 310 of the Revised Penal Code,” (Presidential Decree No. 705 of 1975). Executive Order No. 23 or the Declaring a Moratorium on the Cutting and Harvesting of Timber in the Natural and Residual Forests and Creating the Anti-Illegal Logging Task Force, prohibits the issuance of logging contracts/agreements and renewing tree cutting permits in all natural and residual forests nationwide.

Pursuant to DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-21, the Lawin Forest and Biodiversity Protection System was adopted as the National Strategy for Forest Biodiversity in the country. LAWIN strengthen forest biodiversity protection through the application/system that uses open-source technology for biodiversity and threats monitoring through a smartphone app for electronic encoding of field data and an open-source software for geo-spatial analysis of collected data in forest ecosystems. It integrates forest, biodiversity and threats monitoring, implementation of interventions to address threats and monitoring of the response of the forest ecosystem to these management interventions. It allows management and decision makers to respond directly to threats in a timely manner based on the generated reports.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

PD 705 or the Revised Forestry Code of the Philippines specifically under Section 68 states the following:

authorizes the Secretary of the DENR or his duly authorized representative to order the confiscation of any forest products illegally cut, gathered, removed, or possessed or abandoned, and all conveyances used either by land, water or air in the commission of the offense and to dispose of the same in accordance with pertinent laws, regulations or policies on the matter.

Apprehended forest products including equipment, tools, and conveyances will go under Administrative Confiscation Proceedings (ACP) headed by the respective Community Environmental and Natural Resources Offices. Confiscation is the act of declaring that items become property of the Government of the Republic of the Philippines (DAO-97-32).

The court shall order the confiscation in favor of the government the timber or forest products cut, gathered, collected, removed or possessed as well as the machinery, equipment, implements and tools illegally used in the area where the timber or forest products are found, but only after the case has been filed, tried and decided upon by the court (DAO-97-32).

Forest products forfeited in favor of the government shall be disposed of in accordance with law. The mode of disposition for forest products confiscated/retrieved in favor of the government is through public auction and /or donation. Executive Order No. 23, series of 2011, Section 2.7, states that “the Department of Education shall be given priority in the use of all confiscated logs.” Under Memorandum Order 284, other institutions may also request for donations, and the prioritization shall be in the

following order: Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), School Building Program of the Department of Education Culture and Sports (DECS) and those undertaken by the Department of National Defense/AFP Engineering Brigade, Health Centers, Public Markets, Municipal Buildings, Police Stations, AFP camps, Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), Local Government Units which have jurisdiction over the place where the logs, lumber and other forest products were cut, gathered and/or confiscated, and commitments to provincial, regional and national projects.

Tree Cutting Permit issued to National Government Agencies

Applications for the cutting of trees for all infrastructure projects for the public purposes of National Government Agencies (i.e. DPWH, DepEd) shall be accepted and processed by the concerned CENR Office and will issue the corresponding tree cutting permit within three (3) working days provided that the submitted requirements is complete, (DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16 and 2020-06). Approved forest and wildlife permits were monitored and supervised by DENR Field Office specifically under Enforcement and Monitoring Section under Law Enforcement Program.

Issues Related to Disposition of Confiscated Forest Products

The COA gathered various reports on improper management of confiscated products within the field Offices of the DENR. "Forest products confiscated by the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Offices (PENROs) of Northern Samar and Cebu worth P10.655 million and P1.106 million, respectively, remain idle for almost 10 years. The PENROs of Aklan, Catanduanes, and Capiz were questioned for not initiating disposal proceedings for seized items worth P1.064 million, P2.957

million and P3 million, respectively. The COA said the PENROs of Pangasinan, Pampanga, Aurora, Nueva Ecija, Bulacan and Masbate exposed P16.01 million of seized forest products to misuse and deterioration. The condition and whereabouts of P3.848 million worth of products confiscated by the PENRO of Isabela cannot be determined” (Villanueva, 2021).

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The poor handling of confiscated forest products worth P46.563 million of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) is highlighted in the 2020 audit report of the Commission on Audit. Furthermore, it is mentioned that the cause for “undetermined losses to the government is due to the absence of a clear-cut policy in the management of confiscated, abandoned and seized goods inventory and weak implementation of rules and regulations on the management of confiscated products” (Villanueva, 2021).

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to review the management and disposition of DENR CENRO Lipa with regards to confiscated forest products and turned over logs from approved tree cutting permits issued to NGA's.

Specifically, (1) to determine the status of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs; (2) to recognize/identify the current issues regarding the monitoring and disposition of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs; and (3) to provide recommendation(s) to further strengthen the policy, rules and regulation on the management of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs.

V. RATIONALE

Apprehended/confiscated forest product and turned over logs were hauled and temporarily deposited in the impounding area of DENR CENRO Lipa. As time goes by the economic value of these forest products decreases if it will not be disposed or utilized accordingly.

The study is significant in the DENR in terms of identifying areas for improvement regarding disposition of confiscated forest products and turned over logs, achieve a service excellence and front-runner towards sustainable utilization of natural resources.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The research focuses on finding issues and problems in management and disposition of apprehended and/or confiscated forest product and turned-over logs. The study was able to review and evaluate forestry apprehended incidents in DENR CENRO Lipa from CY 2012 - 2022. Terminal reports from Tree Cutting Permits issued from CY 2019 - 2022 were also evaluated. Only reports on disposition of forest products under the disposition authority at CENRO level were observed. The study did not cover issues and problems in the conduct of the investigation and apprehension procedure in the Field Office. Detailed procedures on the disposition of ACP in the Regional Office - Legal Division were also not part of study.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

DENR CENRO Lipa is located in the Province of Batangas, its jurisdiction covers a total land area of 205,207 hectares of which 192,193.60 ha is classified as Certified Alienable and Disposable, 10,310 ha as Classified Forest Land and the remaining 316 ha is considered as the Unclassified Forest Land. DENR CENRO Lipa has been consistent in the implementation of Environment and Natural Resources protection and law enforcement activities over 5 Districts, 17 Municipalities, 4 Cities and 691 Barangays under its area of responsibility.

Figure 1. Administrative map of CENRO Lipa City.

For CY 2022, through the Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE) of DENR CALABARZON, DENR CENRO Lipa was chosen as the Best CENRO Office and received the Best Organizational Unit Award for

generating the highest revenue in DENR CALABARZON office for the year amounting to Php 74,643,754.27.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

Data Collection

For this study, the secondary data were gathered through (1) documented Administrative Confiscation Proceeding filed in DENR CENRO Lipa; (2) Tree Cutting Permits issued to DPWH; (3) Reports on Apprehended Forest Products Impounded in DENR CENRO LIPA and (4) E-Filing and Monitoring System for Illegal Logging Cases. Primary data were gathered through key informant interviews to be conducted among DENR personnel but not limited to DENR CENRO Lipa and Local Government Unit to validate the issues and problems within the timeline of disposition of logs.

Data Analysis

The research method that is used in this study is descriptive analysis. This descriptive method was used to describe the data and findings that have been obtained during the research to provide a comprehensive discussion and conclusion.

Each filed Apprehension Confiscation Proceedings will be reviewed and evaluated based on the actual duration and process by which cases progressed up to the Decision and Order of Confiscation of Forest Product. From the reviewed ACP, cases with final decision and order will be identified for further study. Apprehended forest products in the impounding area will be monitored and will be categorized the forest products with economic value and deteriorated. The researcher will also look at the management and disposition of the retrieved/turnover logs from the issued Tree Cutting Permits in the National Government Agency (i.e. DPWH, DEPED). Problems/issues encountered by the DENR and LGU related to the process of temporary custody of the forest products and the timeline of disposition of logs less

than 10 cubic meter under the disposition authority at CENRO level will be observed. Generally, the analysis of this study based upon the filling of ACP, from the issuance of permit up to final decision and order, and disposition of forest product.

IX. RESULTS

Table 1 below shows the summary of apprehended/seized and confiscated major forest products in DENR CALABARZON. A total of 1,854.56 cubic meter (cu.m.) volume was apprehended and confiscated, out of these the Province of Quezon gathered the highest apprehended incidents in the Region having a total volume of 1,271.75 cu.m.

Table 1

Apprehended/Seized and Confiscated Major Forest Products in DENR CALABARZON in cubic meters (2016- 2021)

YEAR	PROVINCES					TOTAL
	BATANGAS	CAVITE	LAGUNA	QUEZON	RIZAL	
2016	4.7	-	31.39	157.66	6.54	200.29
2017	15.96	3.88	43.29	204.81	41.63	309.57
2018	13.99	-	19.13	321.33	16.96	371.41
2019	34.54	3.94	34.85	231.99	20.22	325.54
2020	21.33	108.52	41.58	176.13	48.28	395.82
2021	18.22	4.63	29.53	179.83	19.72	251.93
TOTAL	108.74	120.97	199.77	1,271.75	153.35	1,854.56

Table 2

Summary of Apprehended and Confiscated Major Forest Products (2012 – 2022)

YEAR	Logs/Lumber/Flitches	
	Volume (bd.ft)	Estimated Value (P)
2012	6,284.23	440,350.75
2013	1,101.27	186,471.00
2014	-	-
2015	-	-
2016	632.67	695,200.00
2017	196.63	117,978.00
2018	3,650.88	117,390.77
2019	2,824.73	90,155.12
2020	833.33	166,666.67
2021	4,394.64	107,136.52
2022	25,382.34	1,368,634.59
TOTAL	45,300.72	3,289,983.42

Relative to Table 2, DENR CENRO Lipa has apprehended/confiscated 45,300.72 board feet (bd.ft.) of undocumented/abandoned forest products with an estimated value of Php 3,289,983.42. Forestry cases have been filed against individuals conducting illegal ENR activities and eventually confiscation/forfeiture orders were issued.

Table 3

Impounding Area of Apprehended and Confiscated Major Forest Products (2012 – 2022)

Impounding Area	Volume (bd.ft)
DENR CENRO LIPA	41,191.17
Criminal Investigation and Detection Group (CIGD) Batangas	1,390.91
Municipal Police Station	2,248.83
Philippine Ports Authority (PPA) Batangas	469.81
TOTAL	45,300.72

Figure 2. Impounding area of apprehended and confiscated major forest products (2012 – 2022).

Figure 2 shows that 91% or 41,191.17 bd.ft of apprehended / confiscated forest products were turned-over to DENR CENRO Lipa’s impounding area. The remaining 9% of the apprehended forest products were temporarily held in custody by other enforcement agency.

Table 4

Volume of Apprehended and Confiscated Major Forest Products (2012 – 2022) per Species Groupings

SPECIES GROUP	Volume (bd.ft)
Philippine Mahogany Group	1,115.39
Yakal Group	3,952.86
Furniture/Construction Hardwood	33,634.55
Premium Species	4,407.34
Lesser Used Species	2,190.58
TOTAL	45,300.72

Figure 3. Volume of apprehended and confiscated major forest products (2012 – 2022) per species groupings.

Figure 3 shows that most of the apprehended/confiscated forest products belongs to Furniture/Construction Hardwood species, this includes Mahogany, Acacia, Antipolo species with a total of 33,634.55 bd.ft. This is followed by Premium Species (i.e. Narra, Molave) with a total volume of 4,407.34 bd.ft. Yakal and Philippine Mahogany species (i.e. Lauan) was also found in the impounding area with a total volume of 3,952.86 bd.ft and 1,115.39 bd.ft, respectively. Other apprehended/confiscated forest products were classified as Lesser Used species with a total volume of 2,190.58 bd.ft.

Table 5

Status of Apprehended and Confiscated Major Forest Products (2012 – 2022)

Impounded in DENR CENRO Lipa

STATUS	VOLUME (bd.ft)
Intact	35,471.02
Deteriorated	5,720.15
TOTAL	41,191.17

Figure 4. Status of apprehended and confiscated major forest products (2012 – 2022) impounded in DENR CENRO Lipa.

As of CY 2022, 86% or 35,471.02 bd.ft. of apprehended/confiscated forest products were found intact in the impounding area of DENR CENRO Lipa. On the other hand, 5,720.15 bd.ft. of various lumber/flitches were deteriorated and has no economic value.

Table 6

Volume (bd.ft) of Trees Requested for Tree Cutting Permits (TCP'S) Issued to DPWH and Other NGAs (2019-2022)

YEAR	Volume bd.ft
2019	237,906.40
2020	528,541.14
2021	114,727.28
2022	73,015.26
TOTAL	954,190.08

DAO 2018-16 or the Guidelines in the Processing and Issuance of Permits on the Removal and Relocation of Trees Affected by DPWH Projects and DAO 2020-06 or the Amending Certain Provisions and Expanding the Coverage of DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16 was implemented in order to fast track the processing and issuance of tree cutting / earth balling permit relative to the removal or relocation of trees affected by infrastructure project of DPWH and other NGA's (i.e DOTr, DepEd, DA, DOH, CHED, DOE and NIA). As of CY 2022, DENR CENRO Lipa has issued various tree cutting permits to NGA's and with a total volume of 954,190.08 bd.ft.

Table 7.

Accounting of Trees Cut with Tree Cutting Permits (TCPS) Issued to DPWH and Other NGAs (2019-2022)

STATUS	Volume (bd.ft)		
	Turned-over	Not turned-over	Disposed
2019	-	154,107.04	83,799.36
2020	25,910.64	482,588.19	20,042.31
2021	311.09	114,416.19	-
2022	-	73,015.26	-
TOTAL	26,221.73	824,126.68	103,841.67

Timber and other derivable wood materials recovered from the trees cut shall be turned over to DENR CENRO Lipa for proper disposition. Out of 954,190.08 bd.ft. only 26,221.73 bd,ft were properly turned over with documentation / terminal report submitted by DPWH and NGA's. Moreover, 103,841.67 bd.ft of timber were properly disposed accordingly.

Figure 5. Accounting of trees cut with Tree Cutting Permits (TCPs) issued to DPWH and other NGAs CY 2019.

In CY 2019, 65% or 154,107.04 bd.ft of timber were not yet turned-over by DPWH to DENR CENRO Lipa. On the other hand, 83,799.36 bd,ft of timber were donated to MENRO San Juan, Batangas and disposed properly and with accordance to the existing law.

Figure 6. Accounting of trees cut with Tree Cutting Permits (TCPs) issued to DPWH and other NGAs CY 2020.

In CY 2020, 91% or 482,588.19 bd.ft of timber were not yet turned-over by DPWH to DENR CENRO Lipa. Moreover, 5% or 25,910.64 bd.ft of trees cut derivable were turned-over to DENR CENRO Lipa and hauled to the impounding area of the Office, unfortunately, based on the latest monitoring conducted by the Office, all derivable were deteriorated and has no economic value. On the other hand, 20,042.31 bd.ft of timber were disposed and donated to various schools and Philippine Air Force.

Figure 7. Accounting of trees cut with Tree Cutting Permits (TCPs) issued to DPWH and other NGAs CY 2021.

Figure 7 shows that 114,416.19 bd.ft of timber and other derivable were not yet turned-over to DENR CENRO Lipa. Only 311.09 bd.ft of timber from the requested seven trees were hauled to the impounding area of the Office, unfortunately, all derivable were deteriorated and has no economic value.

For CY 2022, 73,015.26 bd.ft of timber and other derivable wood materials were still held in the custody of DPWH / NGA.

X. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To avoid deterioration and loss of the economic value of confiscated forest products and conveyances, impounding areas were established. DENR CALABARZON established ten (10) impounding areas and managed by field offices as shown in Table No. 8. Out of these, there are two (2) impounding areas that are under lease contract, three (3) are located within CENRO compound, one (1) area donated by the LGU, one (1) is lent by a private company, and three (3) are located within government lots.

Table 8

Location of Impounding Areas in DENR CALABARZON

OFFICE	LOCATION	STATUS
PENRO Cavite	FCIE Compound, Brgy. Langkaan, Dasmaringas, Cavite	Lent by Private Company
CENRO Calaca	Brgy. Lumbang na Matanda, Calaca, Batangas	Lease of Contract
CENRO Lipa City	Brgy. Marawoy Lipa City	CENRO Compound
PENRO Laguna	Brgy. Bambang, Los Baños, Laguna	Government Lot
CENRO Sta. Cruz	Brgy. Lamot II, Calauan, Laguna	Donated by LGU
CENRO Catanauan	CENRO Compound, Brgy. 10, Catanauan, Quezon	CENRO Compound
CENRO Calauag	CENRO Compound Brgy. Sabang Dos, Calauag, Quezon	CENRO Compound
CENRO Real	Brgy. Abiawin, Infanta, Quezon	Government Lot

OFFICE	LOCATION	STATUS
CENRO Tayabas	Calumpang Information Center in Brgy. Calumpang, Tayabas City, Quezon	Lease of Contract
PENRO Rizal	Brgy. San Jose, Rodriguez, Rizal	Government Lot

As part of management activities, the field offices are required to conduct an accounting and inventory of all confiscated forest products, conveyances and implements deposited in the impounding area. Additionally, various activities were also conducted such as inventory, sorting, stockpiling, coding, labelling, segregation of waste and cleaning to minimize and/or avoid further deterioration caused by exposure to the elements of nature.

For CY 2012 – 2015, DENR CENRO Lipa’s temporary impounding area was located in Tableria Tan Tao & Saw Mill, Batangas City under Memorandum of Agreement. Moreover, CY 2015 – 2016, the impounding area were relocated to Brgy. Santiago, Sto. Tomas City, Batangas under Lease of Contract. For the following years from CY 2016 – 2021, DENR CENRO Lipa’s Office was transferred from Batangas City to Lipa City, apprehended and/or confiscated forest products were hauled in the adjacent vacant lot of CENRO Lipa. At present, DENR CENRO Lipa have constructed an impounding area adjacent to new office building. Another temporary storage area for apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and conveyances/machineries was identified/established in Brgy. Dagatan, Lipa City.

Issues in the Management of Apprehended/Confiscated Forest Products/Turned over Logs in DENR CENRO Lipa

The problem with the management of apprehended/confiscated forest products as well as with the turned over logs is due to inadequate storage space in the impounding area. Additionally, destruction and a decrease in the value of the apprehended and/or confiscated and turned over forest products is due to limited manpower of the Office to maintain and manage the said forest products, conveyances and implements deposited in the impounding area.

Figure 8. Apprehended/confiscated/turned over forest products and conveyances in impounding area of DENR CENRO Lipa.

Figure 8 shows that the apprehended/confiscated forest products were held in an unsuitable impounding area. Impounding area should be a place for proper

safekeeping of the apprehended/confiscated/turned over forest products however, the identified impounding area of CENRO Lipa has no proper facility and the forest products were exposed to the extreme nature conditions. Missing forest products and parts of impounded conveyances were also reported due to lack of security in the impounding area. The reason for an unsuitable impounding area is the inadequate budget and guidelines of the Department.

Disposition of the Apprehended/Confiscated Forest Product

DENR CENRO Lipa had difficulty in the disposition of the apprehended/confiscated forest product. The Office can only dispose forest products with Confiscation Order and in favor of the government. The particular reason for slow disposition of apprehended / confiscated forest product is due to the pending Criminal Cases filed in the Court. DAO 97-32 stated that forest products which are “subject of a pending case in court or with other appropriate office” are not recommended for disposal. Only, those forest products without claimants or offenders and those found abandoned within forest areas can be disposed of urgently.

Based on the result of the evaluation, out of the twenty-nine (29) recorded major apprehension incidents at the DENR CENRO Lipa which covers the year 2012 to 2022, four (4) Administrative Confiscation Proceeding is still on-going, five (5) with Confiscation Order, two (2) dismissed case, two (2) for filing of criminal case, and eight (8) are still for issuance of confiscation order / pending in the trial court.

One prime example of pending case in the court is the Criminal Case No. 0483-2012 against Gerry Salcedo and Glenson Pangilinan. On August 17, 2012 the DENR CENRO Lipa apprehended seventy-seven (77) pieces of Yakal with a total volume of 703.23 bd.ft. Administrative Confiscation Proceeding (ACP) was already concluded.

Criminal case was already filed at the RTC BR 12 Lipa City, but up to this date, the Office is still waiting for the decision of the Court thus the issuance of the Confiscation Order is still undecided.

Moreover, the Supreme Court designated one hundred seventeen (117) environmental/green courts, fifteen (15) green courts are currently located in CALABARZON of which only three (3) green courts are available in Batangas Province. The slow progress of the filed cases in the court was also affected by the pandemic due to limited movement and availability of the prosecutors. The absence of weak legal support and the non-functioning of green courts is considered as an indicator for a slow judicial system in our country and would result to dismissal of some filled cases.

Accounting of Turned Over Logs from the Issued Tree Cutting Permits

With regards to the turned-over logs from the issued Tree Cutting Permits to DPWH and other National Government Agencies, the problem is the weak compliance of the DPWH / NGA in the terms and conditions specifically on the accounting of the turned-over logs. In addition to that, it was observed that the turned-over logs/timber were not even marketable, not properly cut and the merchantable part of the logs/timber were missing, only the branches were turned-over.

Since, the DENR CENRO Office has a limited storage in the impounding area, the timber and other wood derivable were temporarily held in custody in the Local Government Unit. Relative to that, there are cases that large number of logs were reported missing due to the lack of security in the premises. Additionally, some miscommunication in the part of DENR – DPWH – LGU were observed. Prior to the actual turned-over and submitting of terminal report, the timber and other wood

derivable were already disposed/donated by the LGU without proper documentation and communication with the DENR.

Out of one hundred nineteen (119) permits issued to NGA's since CY 2019, only two (2) cutting permits with a total volume of 52.22 cu.m. have reports on turned-over logs to DENR CENRO Lipa. Based on the inventory of turned-over logs as of December 2022, the logs impounded at CENRO Lipa has been deteriorated and has no economic value.

Continuous coordination with the DPWH and NGA is being conducted, follow-up letters/memorandum was sent to their respective Offices to ensure their prompt compliance in submission of terminal report and turned over of logs.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Without suitable storage/impounding area, destruction and decrease in the value of apprehended/confiscated forest products would result to the increase of the state's losses of assets if the Court decides that the confiscated forest products become government property.

On June 30, 2023 the Department have signed DENR Memorandum Order No. 2023-03 or the Guidelines on the Establishment of Storage Facilities for Turned-Over Logs from Tree Cutting Permits, and Seized and/or Confiscated Illegal Forest Products and the Machinery, Equipment, Tools, Implements, and Conveyances Used in Connection therewith. Relative to the signed DMO, it is highly recommended that the Department should prioritize the establishment of proper storage facility based on the design and layout indicated in DMO 2023-03. In case of existing impounding facilities it is highly advised to allocate funds to maintain and sustain the needs for improvement in the established facility.

For identifying and establishing an impounding area the Department should consider the location, it should be within the jurisdiction of the Field Office and within public or patrimonial land of the state. The impounding area should be constructed in areas that are not prone to flood and/or other factors that may hasten the deterioration of the forest products. A suitable impounding area must be a good place for apprehended/confiscated forest products which are properly stored/filed for the purpose of examination conducted from the investigation until for its final disposition stage. The Department should provide a uniform design and lay-out for impounding facilities and ensure that it is installed with functional CCTV cameras for security purposes.

Furthermore, the Regional Office should create a Regional Council/Technical Working Group that will take responsibility and oversee the monitoring and disposition of the apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs. Relative to that, the Regional Council should maintain a uniform database for the inventory of the apprehended/confiscated forest product emphasizing the status of the items stored, date of disposition and mode of disposition. For proper management, operation, process and disposition, it is recommended that the Property Officer of the DENR Office should be the custodian of the apprehended/confiscated forest products. The officer should possess the Confiscation Order and turned-over logs since the said forest products are already considered as the property of the government. Sufficient manpower/plantilla positions should be created to properly execute the activities (i.e. inventory, sorting, stockpiling, coding, labelling) relative to proper management of the impounding area.

In the absence of a proper storage facility, it is suggested that DENR CENRO Lipa should now start identifying a vacant government lot intended for the establishment of their new storage facility. Because, the Department prioritizes the approval of budget for construction of storage facility in Offices with already identified lot. Moreover, the DENR CENRO Lipa should consider entering into a Memorandum of Agreement with Local Government Unit, there is a high hope that the LGU has a vacant government lot and can be utilized as a storage facility.

The Department should harmonize the policy in terms of tree cutting and disposition of the subject trees for removal and relocation. Additional guidelines for the prompt/proper disposition of turned-over should be considered by the Department. The Department should prohibit the renewal of applications by the National Government Offices which have been incompliant to the accounting procedures of

turned over logs and those with lacking terminal reports related to the previous approved permits.

Prior to cutting activity, it is recommended to implement a leveling off with DENR - DPWH and its contractor - LGU in terms of facilitating the cutting operation and the post requirement for the completion of the activity.

Intensified IEC to the community and stakeholders should be implemented highlighting that only DENR has the authority to properly dispose the forest product. To ensure transparency in the government, the DENR CENRO Lipa should initiate the invitation to bid/donate for forest products available for disposition, it can be done through posting in the public/conspicuous places.

To ensure a strengthened partnership with the LGU, it is recommended that the DENR should enter into a Memorandum of Agreement among all the respective LGU's, emphasizing their responsibility in the proper safeguarding of the timber and other forest products.

Identified issues and problems regarding management and disposition of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs should be raised during the Regional Management Conference for prompt action of the higher Office with regards to the subject matter.

Best Practice of DENR

On October 16, 2023, the DENR Secretary Maria Antonia Yulo Loyzaga together with Binan City Mayor Walfredo Dimaguila, Jr turned-over 100 pieces of fabricated school armchairs to the Binan City Senior High School. The school chairs were made from lumber derived from 13,106 trees cut along the South Luzon Expressway relative to the road-widening project along the stretch of Calamba to San

Pedro in Laguna. The cutting permit was issued by the DENR to the DOTr-TRB-SMC-SLEX Corp. and its contractor, San Miguel Corporation. Laguna Provincial Environment Officer (PENRO) Eriberto Sanos and DENR Regional Executive Director Nilo Tamera spearheaded the initiative.

DENR Regional Orientation and Capacity Building of the National Forest Stock Monitoring System cum Timber Tracking was conducted on October 9-11, 2019 at Marison Hotel, Legazpi City. The National Forest Stock Monitoring System (NFSMS) is a system funded by Philippine Government and the International Tropical Timber Organization (ITTO) that will help the government to plan, monitor and control the Philippine timbers in accordance with internationally accepted standards. It covers activities from pre-harvest inventory, tree marking, felling, bucking, scaling, log/lumber transport, and post-harvest inventory. NFSMS objectives is to (1) develop a 100% “Back-to-Stump” traceability system for wood production; (2) develop a Verified Legal Origin (VLO) featuring automated forest charges calculations based on CTO/CLO documentation; and (3) develop field data entry capabilities and online, configurable, multi-tiered access. The NFSMS project will provide both the DENR and FMB with a transparent, efficient and working Timber Tracking system that will help the government to eliminate various forest illegal activities. The guidelines for adoption in NFSMS is already in progress, various policy were drafted and under review and further consultation by the Departments Policy Technical Working Group. The said project was concluded in 2019, the Department’s hope to adopt the system throughout the forest administration is in line with the approval of the Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) Bill in the legislative body of the government.

The Forest Management Bureau (FMB) conducted a Forestry Fridays in 2020 and 2021; it is a Forestry Webinar Series for all DENR field offices personnel. The

webinar aimed to guide the personnel on the policy implementation, clarify provisions, and identify policy gaps and implementation issues relative to the recently approved forestry related policies and guidelines.

The above-mentioned best practices should be adopted and considered by DENR CENRO Lipa in the implementation of activities relative to Forest Protection and Law Enforcement through intensified Information, Education, Communication (IEC) campaign, a CENRO level databank of approved Forestry Permits, and through a strong partnership with LGU's and Private Sector.

To conclude DENR CENRO Lipa have been consistent and persistent in implementing activities relative to Forest Protection and Law Enforcement within its jurisdiction. However, there are so much more to improve with regards to management and disposition of apprehended and/or confiscated forest products and turned-over logs.

REFERENCES

- DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-21. (2018). *Adoption of Lawin Forest and Biodiversity Protection System as a National Strategy for Forest Biodiversity Protection in the Philippines*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources. https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/fmb_web/?page_id=2539
- DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16. (2018). *Guidelines in the Processing and Issuance of Permits on the Removal and Relocation of Trees Affected by DPWH Projects*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources. https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/fmb_web/?page_id=2539
- DENR Administrative Order No. 2020-06. (2020). *Amending Certain Provisions and Expanding the Coverage of DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16 or the "Guidelines in the Processing and Issuance of Permits on the Removal and Relocation of Trees Affected by DPWH Projects"*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources. https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/fmb_web/?page_id=2539
- DENR Administrative Order No. 97-32. (1997). *Rules for the Administrative Adjudication of Illegal Forest Products and Machinery, Equipment, Tools and Conveyances used in connection therewith*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources.
- DENR Memorandum Order No. 2023-02. (2023). *Guidelines on the Establishment of Storage Facilities for Turned-Over Logs from Tree Cutting Permits, and Seized and/or Confiscated Illegal Forest Products and the Machinery, Equipment, Tools, Implements, and Conveyances Used in Connection therewith*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources. https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/fmb_web/?page_id=2539

DENR Region IV-A CALABARZON. (2021). *Annual Report*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources.

DENR Region IV-A CALABARZON. (2021). *ENR Information and Statistic Report*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources.

DENR Region IV-A CALABARZON. (2022). *Annual Report*. Department of Environment and Natural Resources.

Executive Order No. 23. (2011). *Declaring a Moratorium on the Cutting and Harvesting of Timber in the Natural and Residual Forests and Creating the Anti-Illegal Logging Task Force*.

<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2011/02/01/executive-order-no-23-s-2011/>

Executive Order No. 192. (1987). *Providing for the Reorganization of the Department of Environment, Energy and Natural Resources, Renaming it as the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, and for other Purposes*.

<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1987/06/10/executive-order-no-192-s-1987/>

Faure, M. G., Goodwin, M.E. A., & Weber, F. (2010). Bucking the Kuznets curve: Designing effective environmental regulation in developing countries. *Virginia Journal of International Law*, 51(1), 95-156.

https://pure.uvt.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/1295481/Goodwin_Bucking_the_Kuznets_Curve_110114_publishers_embargo1y.pdf

Forest Management Bureau. (2019). *Development and Testing of National Forest Stock Monitoring System (FSMS) with Improved Governance Capabilities at All Levels of the Forest Administration Technical Report*.

https://www.itto.int/files/itto_project_db_input/2982/technical/PD-599-11-R1-M-Technical%20Report.pdf?v=1709269446

- Forestry Development Center. (2004). *Simplified and Harmonized Forestry Regulatory Procedures of the Philippines: Terminal Report*. University of the Philippines Los Banos Foundation, Incorporated.
<https://faspselib.denr.gov.ph/node/1667>
- Imperatives, S. (1987). *Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our common future*. <http://www.ask-force.org/web/Sustainability/Brundtland-Our-Common-Future-1987-2008.pdf>
- Joint FMB-BMB Technical Bulletin No. 2016-01. (2016). *Enhancing Forest Protection through application of the LAWIN Forest and Biodiversity Protection System*. Forest Management Bureau - Biodiversity Management Bureau.
https://forestry.denr.gov.ph/fmb_web/?page_id=2539
- Memorandum Order No. 162. (1993). *Providing Guidelines for the Disposition of Confiscated Logs, Lumber and Other Forest Products for Public Infrastructure Projects and Other Purposes*.
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1993/08/19/memorandum-order-no-162-s-1993/>
- Memorandum Order No. 284. (1995). *Amending Section 4 of Memorandum Order No. 162, dated August 19, 1993, which provided the Guidelines for the Disposition of Confiscated Logs, Lumber, And Other Forest Products for Public Infrastructure Projects and Other Purposes*.
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1995/06/05/memorandum-order-no-284-s-1995/>
- Pescott, M. J., & Durst, P. B. (2010). *Reviewing FLEG progress in Asia and the Pacific. Forest law enforcement and governance: progress in Asia and the Pacific*.

<http://www.apafri.org/activities/Bhutan2013/Publication/M6%20Forest%20Law%20Enforcement%20and%20Government.pdf#page=11>

Philippine Judicial Academy. (2012). *Citizen's Handbook on Environmental Justice*.

<https://www.ombudsman.gov.ph/UNDP4/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/s-HanBook-CC1.pdf>

Presidential Decree No. 705. (1975). *Revising Presidential Decree No. 389,*

otherwise known as the Forestry Reform Code of the Philippines.

<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1975/05/19/presidential-decree-no-705-s-1975/>

Villanueva, R., & Marcelo, E. (2021, July 29). COA flags DENR over P46.5 million seized forest products. *philstar Global*.

<https://www.philstar.com/nation/2021/07/29/2115926/coa-flags-denr-over-p465-million-seized-forest-products>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Trees Species Apprehended and/or Confiscated in DENR CENRO Lipa's Impounding Area

Common Name	Scientific Name	Species Group	Ecological Status (IUCN)
White Lauan	<i>Shorea contorta</i>	Philippine Mahogany Group	Least Concern
Yakal	<i>Shorea astylosa</i>	Yakal Group	Endangered
Acacia	<i>Albizia saman</i>	Furniture/ Construction Hardwood	Threatened
Mahogany	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i>	Furniture/ Construction Hardwood	Vulnerable
Antipolo	<i>Artocarpus blancoi</i>	Furniture/ Construction Hardwood	Least Concern
Narra	<i>Pterocarpus indicus</i>	Premium Species	Endangered
Molave	<i>Vitex parviflora</i>	Premium Species	Least Concern
Tindalo	<i>Azelia rhomboidea</i>	Lesser Used Species	Vulnerable
Mango	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Lesser Used Species	Data Deficient
Gmelina	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Lesser Used Species	Least Concern

APPENDIX B

Inventory/Summary for Administrative Confiscation Proceedings in DENR CENRO Lipa

DATE APPREHENDED	PLACE OF APPREHENSION	APPREHENDING OFFICER	FOREST PRODUCTS INVOLVED				PERSONS INVOLVED/ ABANDONED	CUSTODIAN	IMPOUNDING AREA	STATUS
			Pcs.	Species	Kind	Volume				
17-Nov-22	Brgy. San Pedro I. Malver, Batangas	CENRO Allan Willard M. Estillore, FTII Francisco S. Africa, FTI Ariel Y. Maglinao FR Marilou Tarcelo, FR Sofia M. Banuelos and Francis Nicko C. Evangelista		Assorted		226,1457	Php. 11,307,733.00	Fiordaliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Criminal case are already filed and Administrative Confiscation Proceeding is on-going. The said forest products and implements hauled to the impounding area of our Office for safekeeping
12-Apr-22	Brgy. Halang, Lipa City, Batangas	FI Alvin B. Hualala, FTII Francisco S. Africa FTI Ariel Y. Maglinao and FR Sofia M. Banuelos	218	Narra	Lumber/Filiches	1808.42	Php. 180,841.67	Fiordaliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Administrative Confiscation Proceeding is on-going. The said forest products were hauled to the impounding area of our Office in Brgy. Maraway, Lipa City, Batangas for safekeeping.
7-Apr-22	Brgy. Catandala, Ibaan, Batangas	FI Alvin B. Hualala, and FTII Francisco S. Africa		Mango		480 board feet	Php. 23,991.67	Fiordaliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Administrative Confiscation Proceeding is on-going. The said forest products were hauled to the impounding area of our Office in Brgy. Maraway, Lipa City, Batangas for safekeeping.
29-Mar-22	Brgy. Mapulo, Tayasan, Batangas	FI Alvin B. Hualala, FTII Francisco S. Africa and FTI Ariel Y. Maglinao		Mango		479.25 Board feet	33,068.25	Abandoned	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Administrative Confiscation Proceeding is on-going. The said forest products were hauled to the impounding area of our Office in Brgy. Maraway, Lipa City, Batangas for safekeeping.
June 14, 2021	Brgy. Sambil, Mataas na Kalbay, Batangas	DENR-CENRO Lipa personnel	66	28 pcs Mutawin 38 pcs Antipolo	Lumber	1,052 bdf.	Php 84,160	Fiordaliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order
March 25, 2021	Brgy. Batangas, Batangas City, Batangas	1st PM/FC, CIDT Batangas, Batangas CPS (PLT ROMMEL P MAGNO)	10	Narra	Lumber	210.98 bdf more or less	21,098.00	Lourdez Sanchez Y. Layug, Ricardo Carpio Y Pandong, Angelo Briones Y. Nulud, Rogelio Layug Y. Cayanan and Renren Sanchez Y. Layug	CIDG Batangas, Camp Gen. Malver, Kumintang, Batangas City	Decided Found guilty for violation of PD 705 (CC No. 21-27887)
January 25, 2021	Brgy. Laurel, Tayasan, Batangas	CIDG Batangas City	12 pcs	Mahogany	Lumber	78.66	PI. 573.22	Hilario Antenor Avelo Francisco Bale Manolito	CIDG Batangas, Camp Gen. Malver, Kumintang, Batangas City	For Filing
January 12, 2021	San Rafael, Sto Tomas City, Batangas	Sto Tomas Police	164 pcs	Yakal	Lumber	3,053 Bdf. Ft.	P305-300	Nixon de la cruz Y. Capinlac, Jovic Facinabao Louie Baring Y. Diaz, John John Sumaway Y. Icaband	DENR-CENRO Lipa	For Filing
December 11, 2020	Poblacion 7, cuenca, Batangas	Cuenca, Municipal Police Station	80 pcs	Mango	Lumber	833.33 Bdf.	P 166,866.67	Christian Abos Lucanas Wilson Gupto Martinez	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Dismissed
October 5, 2019	Brgy. Pingtung-Juan, San Jose, Batangas	San Jose Municipal Police	51 pcs	Acacia	Lumber	1,696 Bdf. Ft.	P67,840	Arthur Lopez Y. Reposa and Gerardo Ramirez	LGU	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order
March 26, 2019	Brgy. Bagong Pook, San Jose, Batangas	DENR-CENRO Lipa personnel	14 pcs 30 pcs	Acacia lgw	Lumber	441.83 bdf.	7,953.00	Ryan Hernandez Ayas Negro, Michelle Hroyoki	LGU	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order

January 22, 2019	Brgy. Manggas, Padre Garcia, Batangas	DENR-CENRO Lipa personnel	7 pcs 3 pcs	Mahogany Gmelina	Lumber	575.9 bdf.	10,366.12	Rudolfo Magtaas	Flordeliza M. Olave Demetrio Gabon (Brgy. Councilor)	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Dismissed
March 5, 2019	Brgy. Sta Clara, Sto Tomas, Batangas	DENR-CENRO Lipa personnel	24 pcs	Mahogany	Lumber	111 bdf.	3,996.00	Abandoned		LGU	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order. Crime Case No. 20590; both accused pleaded GUILTY to a lesser offence and sentenced to suffer penalty of imprisonment from six (6) months and one (1) day to two (2) years and four (4) months in order dated February 6, 2019.
August 25, 2018	Batangas International Port, Sta Clara, Batangas City	401 Maritime Police PPA Batangas	28 pcs	Lauan	Lumber	1,115.39 bdf.	61,348.65	Roberto Arroza and Norman Dolor	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	
August 25, 2018	Batangas International Port, Sta Clara, Batangas City	401 Maritime Police PPA Batangas	76 pcs	assorted	Lumber	469.81 bdf.	16,805.54	Marilyn Jose Y. Cedenio and Ricardo Catalos Y. Buencido	401 Maritime Police PPA Batangas	PPA Batangas	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order
July 2, 2018	Brgy. Ilugan Rosario, Batangas	DENR-CENRO Lipa personnel	21 pcs 74 pcs	Acacia Mango	Lumber	2,065.68 bdf.	39,236.58	Reymundo Dimaano	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Motion for Reconsideration. Denied ongoing trial
December 5, 2017	Brgy. Tingali, Batangas City	Batangas city, ENRO, Batangas City, Police	24 pcs	Yakal	Lumber	196.63 bdf.	117,978	Lemuel Asedillo, Crizaldo Valiente, Manin Verz, Antonio Asedillo, Richard de Torres, Marvin Acueza, Dario Asedillo, Ramil Linares, Joseph Llares	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Crime Case No. 23181 DECIDED Guilty
May 20, 2016	Brgy. Sawang Lobo, Batangas	PNP Lobo, Batangas	31 pcs 34 pcs	Tindalo Molave	Lumber	399 bdf. 234.67 bdf.	437,800.00 257,400.00	Randolph Maalihan, June Hernandez, Michael de Chavez, Mario Guinio	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Decided, Waiting for issuance of confiscation order
October 5, 2013	Brgy. Sta Clara, Batangas City	PNP Batangas Provincial Public Safety Company, Technical Support Platoon led by PCINSP Jose O. Naparato Jr.	10 pcs 23 pcs	Naira Tindalo	Lumber	1,101.27 bdf. 2.59 cubic meters	186,471.00	Jonathan Mendoza Nasai Bonggar	Flordeliza M. Olave	CIDG Batangas, Camp Gen. Makar, Kuminang, Batangas City	Crime Case No. 20490 Decided Guilty
August 4, 2012	Brgy. San Roque, Sto Tomas, Batangas	CENRO L. Salac, Batangas Prov. Task Force VSR Sto Tomas Municipal Police station	326 pcs	Mahogany	Lumber	5,581 bdf.	299,704.75	Victor Claro	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Crime case No. 16-079375 ARCHIVED
August 17, 2012	Brgy. Banay-Banay, Lipa City, Batangas	PNP Lipa City, Batangas	77 pcs	Yakal	Lumber	703.23 bdf.	140,646	Gerry Salcedo and Glenison Pangilinan	Flordeliza M. Olave	DENR-CENRO Lipa	Case pending RTC BR-12 Lipa City (CC-0483-2012) Submitted for decision

APPENDIX C

Tree Cutting Permit Issued to NGA for CY 2019

TREE CUTTING PERMIT ISSUED TO DPWH FOR CY 2019										
No.	Permittee	Location	Permit No.	Date Issued	Date Expired	No. of Trees		Total	Volume (cu.m)	
						Naturally Grown	Planted			
1	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgys. Pulong Nigan and Poblacion of Mabini, Batangas	04232019-01-A	April 23, 2019	June 7, 2019	4		4	1.59	
2	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgys. Sico, Calicanto and Maraykit, San Juan, Batangas	05202019-02-A	May 20, 2019	July 4, 2019		196	196	127.4	
3	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgys. Buhay na Sapa, San Juan, Batangas	05202019-03-A	May 20, 2019	July 4, 2019		214	214	70.24	
4	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgys. Poblacion and Mabing na Bundok, Lobo, Batangas	06102019-04-A	June 10, 2019	July 25, 2019		11	11	3.28	
5	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgy. San Miguel, Lobo, Batangas.	07082019-05-A	July 8, 2019	August 22, 2019	72	166	228	66.6	
6	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgy. Malapad na Parang and Balabat, Lobo, Batangas	07082019-06-A	July 8, 2019	August 22, 2019	13	8	21	4.1	
7	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgy. Malapad na Parang, Lobo, Batangas.	07082019-07-A	July 8, 2019	August 22, 2019	8	52	60	20.53	
8	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgy. Panarag East, Batangas City, Batangas	07092019-08-A	July 10, 2019	August 24, 2019		92	92	109.55	
9	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgy. Tulo, Batangas City, Batangas	07092019-09-A	July 10, 2019	August 24, 2019		127	127	144.1	
10	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Alexander M. Caponpon	Brgy. San Agustin, Ibaan, Batangas	07112019-10-A	July 10, 2019	August 24, 2019		28	28	9.51	
11	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Edwin D. Abriogonda	Brgys. Manghiniao I, Balayong & As-is, Bauan, Batangas	09032019-11-A	September 5, 2019	October 20, 2019		7	7	4.2	
TOTAL						97	891	988	561.1	

APPENDIX D

Tree Cutting Permit Issued to NGA for CY 2020

NO.	PERMIT NO.	NAME OF PERMITTEE	LOCATION	NO. OF TREES TO BE CUT			Volume (cu.m)	DATE ISSUED
				Planted	Naturally Grown	Total		
1	01162020-01-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Sta. Clara, Batangas City, Batangas	18	0	18	0.83	January 16, 2020
2	01162020-02-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	4	3	7	0.59	January 16, 2020
3	01162020-03-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	9	0	9	0.04	January 16, 2020
4	01162020-04-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	27	15	42	2.87	January 16, 2020
5	01162020-05-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	7	0	7	0.22	January 16, 2020
6	01162020-06-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	7	0	7	0.22	January 16, 2020
7	01162020-07-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	6	0	6	0.07	January 16, 2020
8	01162020-08-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	23	0	23	0.07	January 16, 2020
9	02202020-09-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	31	0	31	0.21	February 24, 2020
10	02202020-10-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	17	0	17	0.05	February 24, 2020
11	02202020-11-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer Edwin D. Abrigonda	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	66	0	66	11.96	February 24, 2020
12	06162020-12-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas III District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Prescila R. Ramos	Brgy. Trapiche, Tanauan City, Batangas	9	0	9	2.83	June 16, 2020
13	08112020-13-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgys. Sawang, Mabilog na Bundok, Olo Olo and Poblacion, Lobo, Batangas	119	44	163	37.3	August 11, 2020
14	08172020-14-A	DPWH SLEX TR 4	Brgys. San Felix, San Pablo, San Jose, & San Juan, Sto. Tomas, Batangas	1521	2248	3769	80.955	November 6, 2020
15	08172020-15-A	DPWH SLEX TR 4	Brgys. San Antonio, San Miguel, San Pablo, Santiago and San Pedro, Sto. Tomas, Batangas	4101	1135	5236	130.168	November 6, 2020
16	08202020-16-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City, Batangas	3	0	3	2.1	August 20, 2020
17	08202020-17-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Concepcion, Batangas City, Batangas	6	0	6	1.49	August 20, 2020
18	08262020-18-A	NATIONAL IRRIGATION ADMINISTRATION Charlie D. Ibarrola, Division Manager A	Brgy. Sico I, San Juan, Batangas	34	4	38	4.74	September 11, 2020

19	09112020-19-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Laurel, Mabini, Batangas	30	0	30	6.63	September 11, 2020
20	09112020-20-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgys. Balatbat and San Miguel, Lobo, Batangas	6	476	482	26.24	September 11, 2020
21	09112020-21-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgy. Laiya Ibabao, San Juan, Batangas	138	10	148	26.21	September 14, 2020
22	09112020-22-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgys. Laiya Ibabao and Laiya Aplaya, San Juan, Batangas	88	21	109	6.89	September 14, 2020
23	09232020-23-A	DPWH SLEX TR 4	Brgys. San Bartolome, San Vicente, San Pablo and San Antonio, Sto. Tomas, Batangas	1331	1876	3207	209.083	November 6, 2020
24	09242020-24-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas III District Engineering Office c/o Engr. Prescila R. Ramos	Brgy. San Miguel, Sto. Tomas, Batangas	1	0	1	0.129	September 24, 2020
25	09302020-25-A	BSU	Brgy. Alangilan, Batangas	2	0	2	0.5155	September 30, 2020
26	10192020-25-B	Sta Cruz Elementary School	Brgy. Sta. Cruz, Sto. Tomas	18	0	18	4.99	October 19, 2020
27	11032020-27-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Malapad na Parang, Lobo, Batangas	0	10	10	1.5057	October 20, 2020
28	11032020-28-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgys. Tulo and Paharang East, Batangas City, Batangas	26	0	26	2.4773	November 05, 2020
29	11032020-29-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgys. Balintawak and Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas	41	127	168	7.7303	November 05, 2020
30	11032020-30-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgys. Balintawak and Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas	192	372	564	21.8568	November 06, 2020
31	11092020-31-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgys. Puting Buhangin – Mabalano & Talahiban II, San Juan Batangas	5	0	5	3.9093	November 06, 2020
32	11092020-32-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgy. Puting Buhangin, San Juan Batangas	433	11	444	148.4825	November 11, 2020
33	11092020-33-A	Philippine Air Force Air Education, Training and Doctrine Command	Fernando Air Base, Lipa City, Batangas	63	1	64	38.3389	November 16, 2020
34	11162020-34-A	Balas Buco Sta. Maria National Highschool	Brgy. Balas, Talisay,	7	0	7	1.8152	November 25, 2020
35	11252020-35-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Pagkilatan, Batangas City, Batangas	0	63	63	4.772	November 25, 2020
36	11252020-36-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Banaba Center, Batangas City, Batangas	14	0	14	0.4145	November 25, 2020
37	12012020-37-A	Senator Maria Kalaw Katigbak Elementary School	Brgy. Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas	2	0	2	1.61	December 1, 2020
38	12072020-38-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o Sonia D. Paglicauan, OIC - District Engineer	Brgy. Kumintang Ibaba, Batangas City, Batangas	45	0	45	6.9926	December 7, 2020
39	12072020-39-A	DILG c/o Provincial Engineering Office Batangas	Brgys. Lalayat, San Jose – Burgahan, Cuenca – Pinagrusan, Alitaglag – Gelerang Kawayan, San Pascual, Bauan Provincial Road (Phase IV), San Pascual, Batangas	13	3	16	0.6145	December 7, 2020
40	12152020-40-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas IV District Engineering Office c/o Rody Angulo - District Engineer	Brgy. Bulacnin, Lipa City, Batangas	88	96	184	6.4942	December 15, 2020
41	DENR-IV-A-02242020-04B	Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) SLEX TR4 Issued by Regional Office	Brgy. San Juan, Sto. Tomas	1575	931	2506	61.11	
42	DENR-IV-A-10282020-057B	Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) SLEX TR4 Issued by Regional Office	Brgys. Santiago, San Rafael, San Antonio, San Bartolome, San Miguel, San Vicente and San Pedro, Sto. Tomas	2487	4471	6958	221.232	10/28/2020
42	DENR-IV-A-10282020-058B	Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) SLEX TR4 Issued by Regional Office	Brgy. San Felix, Sto. Tomas	6289	1133	7422	159.803	10/28/2020
Total				18902	13050	31952	1246.5593	

APPENDIX E
Tree Cutting Permit Issued to NGA for CY 2021

NO.	PERMIT NO.	NAME OF PERMITTEE	LOCATION	NO. OF TREES TO BE		DATE ISSUED	REQUIRED NO. OF REPLACEMENT	VOLUME (cu.m)
				Planted	Natural			
1	01162020-01-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A Batangas II District Engineering Office c/o District Engineer, Sonia Paglicawan	Brgy. Sta. Clara, Batangas City, Batangas	18	0	January 16, 2021	900	10,3927
2	01212021-02-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Tulo, Batangas City	0	34	January 25, 2021	3400	1,285
3	01262021-03-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Talumpok Siangan, Batangas City	82	59	January 25, 2021	10000	7,1969
4	01262021-04-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Sawang, Lobo	175	64	January 25, 2021	15150	36,8495
5	02032021-05-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Balagtas, Batangas City	41	10	February 3, 2021	3050	13,5099
6	02032021-06-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Sta. Cruz, Sto. Tomas, Batangas	12	1	February 3, 2021	650	7,89
7	02092021-07-A	BSU Malvar	BSU – JPLPC Malvar	2	0	February 9, 2021	100	2,3101
8	02222021-08-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Tiquian, San Jose and San Car	18	8	February 22, 2021	1700	7,2113
9	02222021-09-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Puring Kahoy, Rosario and Muzol	45	0	February 22, 2021	2250	43,9406
10	02222021-10-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Bolbok Elementary School Brgy. Bolbok, Lipa City, Batangas	7	0	February 22, 2021	350	0,7337
11	03022021-11-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Anilao East & Pulong Niogan, Ma	64	94	March 2, 2021	12,600	26,7
12	03022021-12-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Mataas na Lupa & Paisahingin, S	55	20	March 2, 2021	4750	13,0846
13	03022021-13-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Balayong & San Antonio San Pascual and Brigs. Manghirao I, II, III and IV, Bauan, Batangas	17	9	March 2, 2021	1750	4,89
14	03042021-14-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brigs. Malainin, Ibaan, Batangas	61	38	March 4, 2021	6850	6,002
15	03022021-15-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Solo, Mabini, Batangas	0	31	March 2, 2021	3100	4,0546

16	03122021-16-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Pulung Anahao, Mabini, Batangas	3	0	March 12, 2021	150	2,5425
17	03182021-17-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Catandala, Batangas City, Batangas	131	0	March 18, 2021	6650	6,3643
18	03292021-18-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas	7	0	March 29, 2021	350	0,9357
19	05212021-19-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Marawoy, Lipa City, Batangas	2	0	May 20, 2021	100	4,2646
20	06232021-20-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Masaya, Rosario, Batangas	19	22	June 23, 2021	3150	10,7303
21	06232021-21-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. San Carlos, Rosario, Batangas	50	43	June 23, 2021	6800	5,9972
22	07152021-22-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Tinga Labac, Batangas City, Batangas	56	29	July 15, 2021	5700	18,7109
23	07292021-23-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Sawang, Lobo, Batangas	47	31	July 29, 2021	5450	12,9272
24	07292021-24-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Poblacion 4, Bataan, Batangas	22	1	July 29, 2021	1200	5,4744
25	07302021-25-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Sta. Cruz, Sto. Tomas City, Batangas	3	12	July 30, 2021	1350	0,9726
26	08092021-26-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Briggs, Tilambo & Mabuyabas, Taysan, Bataan	25	16	August 13, 2021	2850	2,1851
27	08092021-27-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Baitatbat, Lobo, Batangas	42	25	August 9, 2021	4600	6,7546
28	08042021-28-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Banaadero, Tanauan City, Batangas	1		August 4, 2021	100	0,5891
29	08042021-29-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Poblacion, Sto. Tomas City, Batangas	2		August 4, 2021	100	2,9438
30	09162021-30-A	DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS Region IV-A	Brgy. Muntingpubo, Lipa City, Batangas	10	52	September 16, 2021	5700	3,17
Total				1017	599		110750	260,1905

APPENDIX F

Tree Cutting Permit Issued to NGA for CY 2022

NO.	PERMIT NO.	NAME OF PERMITTEE	ADDRESS	NO. OF TREES		LOCATION OF TREES TO BE CUT	TOTAL VOLUME (CU. M.)	DATE APPROVED
				Planted	Naturally Grown			
1	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03012022-01 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Banaba, Batangas City, Batangas	93	21	Banaba, Batangas City, Batangas	3.7249	03/01/2022
2	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03012022-02 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Malapad na Parang, Lobo, Batangas	4	14	Malapad na Parang, Lobo, Batangas	3.6953	03/21/2022
3	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03222022-03 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Tbga Labac, Batangas City	67	27	Tbga Labac, Batangas City	18.8229	03/22/2022
4	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-04 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Subokan, San Juan	68	26	Subokan, San Juan	13.1534	03/23/2022
5	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-05 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Palahanan I, San Juan	74	6	Palahanan I, San Juan	20.7974	03/23/2022
6	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-06 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Palahanan II & Muzon, San Juan	52	10	Palahanan II & Muzon, San Juan	13.5486	03/23/2022
7	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-07 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Pina, Tayasan	100	52	Pina, Tayasan	4.3422	03/23/2022
8	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-08 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Chalacub II, San Juan	69	9	Chalacub II, San Juan	26.4024	03/23/2022
9	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-09 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Tpaz, San Juan	35	0	Tpaz, San Juan	13.7007	03/23/2022
10	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-10 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Tpaz, San Juan	10	0	Tpaz, San Juan	2.6083	03/23/2022
11	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03232022-11 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Bataan, San Juan	46	14	Bataan, San Juan	9.5455	03/23/2022
12	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03302022-12 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Bucato, Tayasan	57	32	Bucato, Tayasan	2.2227	03/30/2022
13	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 03302022-13 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Mapub, Tayasan	62	8	Mapub, Tayasan	10.6350	03/30/2022
14	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 04182022-14 A	Regional Office, DPWH	Balagtas, Batangas	1	39	Balagtas, Batangas	2.6995	04/18/2022
15	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 04182022-15 A	Regional Office, DPWH	Cuta, Batangas	4	11	Cuta, Batangas	1.4862	04/18/2022
16	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 05102022-16 A	3rd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Emmanuel, Cuena	2	2	Emmanuel, Cuena	0.2229	05/16/2022
17	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 05192022-17 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	San Miguel, Lobo	32	69	San Miguel, Lobo	13.0547	05/19/2022
18	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 05232022-18 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Banaba South & Banaba West, Batangas City	14	6	Banaba South & Banaba West, Batangas City	3.0967	05/23/2022
19	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 06062022-19 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Nana, Rosario	5	0	Nana, Rosario	2.0417	06/06/2022
20	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 06132022-20 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Laurel, Mabini	112	14	Laurel, Mabini	9.8164	06/13/2022
21	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 06212022-21 A	Regional Office, DPWH	Sto. Nino & Calamias, Ibaan	104	27	Sto. Nino & Calamias, Ibaan	11.2633	06/21/2022
22	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 06222022-22 A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Sawang & Soloc, Lobo	134	41	Sawang & Soloc, Lobo	18.377	06/22/2022
23	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 07052022-23 A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Laurel, Tayasan	2	2	Laurel, Tayasan	1.0523	07/05/2022
24	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa - 07292022-24 A	Regional Office, DPWH	Brgy. Cuta, Batangas City	50	0	Brgy. Cuta, Batangas City	0.2591	07/29/2022

25	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa-08042022-25-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Kunitang Ilaya, Batangas City	1	0	Brgy. Kunitang Ilaya, Batangas City	0.2756	08/04/2022
26	DENR-IV-A-CENRO Lipa-08112022-26-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Libjo, Batangas City	4	0	Brgy. Libjo, Batangas City	1.9346	08/11/2022
27	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-08172022-27-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Manghinio I, Bauan	38	1	Brgy. Manghinio I, Bauan	3.5395	08/16/2022
28	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-09082022-28-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Tubo, Batangas City	17	29	Brgy. Tubo, Batangas City	4.6661	09/08/2022
29	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-09142022-29-A	3rd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Sampaloc, Talisay, Batangas	10	0	Brgy. Sampaloc, Talisay, Batangas	5.9319	09/14/2022
30	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-09212022-30-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Alangilan, Batangas City, Batangas	0	4	Brgy. Alangilan, Batangas City, Batangas	7.9734	09/21/2022
31	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-09222022-31-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Banaba Center, Batangas City, Batangas	4	5	Brgy. Banaba Center, Batangas City, Batangas	0.9063	09/22/2022
32	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-10052022-32-A	3rd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgys. Malaking Pulo & Santol, Tamauan City, Batangas	1936	2066	Brgys. Malaking Pulo & Santol, Tamauan City, Batangas	45.0847	10/05/2022
33	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-10052022-33-A	4th District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Tipaz, San Juan, Batangas	0	6	Brgy. Tipaz, San Juan, Batangas	0.7498	10/05/2022
34	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-11022022-34-A	2nd District Engineering Office, DPWH, Batangas	Brgy. Tahumpok Silangan, Batangas City, Batangas	36	3	Brgy. Tahumpok Silangan, Batangas City, Batangas	1.8589	11/02/2022
35	DENR-IV-A-CENRO-12142022-35-A	Jovel G. Mendoza/ DPWH	Brgy. Sto. Nifo, Lipa City, Batangas	2491	120	Brgy. Sto. Nifo, Lipa City, Batangas	86.5466	12/15/2022
							172.2058	

APPENDIX G
DENR Memorandum Order No. 2023-02

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Environment and Natural Resources
Visayas Avenue, Diliman, 1100 Quezon City
Tel. Nos. (632) 8929-6626 to 29; (632) 8929-6633; to 35
Email: web@denr.gov.ph Website: www.denr.gov.ph

JUN 30 2023

DENR MEMORANDUM ORDER
No. 2023- 02

SUBJECT: GUIDELINES ON THE ESTABLISHMENT OF STORAGE FACILITIES FOR TURNED-OVER LOGS FROM TREE CUTTING PERMITS, AND SEIZED AND/OR CONFISCATED ILLEGAL FOREST PRODUCTS AND THE MACHINERY, EQUIPMENT, TOOLS, IMPLEMENTS, AND CONVEYANCES USED IN CONNECTION THEREWITH

Pursuant to Presidential Decree No. 705, as amended, or the "Revised Forestry Code of the Philippines", Executive Order No. 192, Series of 1987, entitled, "Providing for the Reorganization of the Department of Environment, Energy and Natural Resources, Renaming it as the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, and for Other Purposes", DENR Administrative Order (DAO) No. 2021-11, "Guidelines in the Processing and Issuance of Permits for the Cutting, Removal and Relocation of Naturally Growing Trees", DAO No. 1997-32, entitled, "1997 Rules for the Administrative Adjudication of Illegal Forest Products and the Machinery, Equipment, Tools and Conveyances Used in Connection Therewith", the following guidelines on the establishment of storage facilities for turned-over logs from tree cutting permits, and seized and/or confiscated illegal forest products, including machinery, equipment, tools, implements and conveyances used in connection therewith, are hereby promulgated.

I. DEFINITION OF TERMS

- a. Forest Products – refers to timber including lumber, pulpwood, firewood, bark, tree top, resin, gum, wood, oil, honey, beeswax, nipa, rattan, charcoal, or other forest growth, such as but not limited to grass, shrub, flowering plants in forestlands, and others.
- b. Illegal Forest Products – any forest products that are removed, cut, collected, processed, and/or transported: (i) without the requisite authorization or permit; (ii) with incomplete required supporting documents; (iii) with genuine authorizations or permits and/or supporting documentation that have an expired validity, have been canceled or that contain forged entries; or (iv) with spurious (fake) authorizations, permits, and/or supporting documentation.

- c. Storage Facilities – closed structure used for storing turned-over logs, seized and/or confiscated illegal forest products, and machinery, equipment, tools, implements and conveyances used in the possession, gathering, collecting, and/or processing of illegal forest products.
- d. Tree Cutting Permit (TCP) – a collective term for all the permits issued by the DENR for the cutting or removing of trees such as, but not limited to, Special Tree Cutting Permits, Special Private Land Timber Permits, Private Land Timber Permit, and Tree Cutting Permit.
- e. Turned-Over Logs – refers to logs derived through the cutting or removing of trees with the authority of a Tree Cutting Permit that are surrendered to the DENR for proper disposition.
- f. Conveyance – any mode or type or class of vehicle or craft or any other means used for transportation either on land, water, air, or any combination thereof, whether motorized or not, used for or in taking and/or maintaining temporary or permanent possession or control, gathering, collecting, processing, disposing of, or otherwise transporting, moving or transferring illegal forest products.

II. ESTABLISHMENT OF STORAGE FACILITIES

All Community Environment and Natural Resources Offices (CENROs) and Implementing Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Offices (Implementing PENROs), and Regional Offices, in the case of NCR, shall establish storage facilities for turned-over logs from Tree Cutting Permits (TCPs) and seized and/or confiscated illegal forest products, including machinery, equipment, tools, implements, and conveyances used in illegal logging activities.

A. SITE REQUIREMENTS

The CENROs and Implementing PENROs, or the Regional Office in the case of the National Capital Region (NCR) shall identify strategic sites that are adjacent to their offices or within their area of jurisdiction for the construction of storage facilities, provided that the storage facilities shall be established within public or patrimonial land of the state. Further, the storage facilities shall be constructed in areas that are not prone to flood and/or other factors that may cause or hasten the deterioration of the turned-over logs from TCPs and seized and/or confiscated illegal products and the machinery, equipment, tools, implements, and conveyances.

B. DESIGN AND LAY-OUT OF STORAGE FACILITIES

The storage facilities shall be in accordance with the design and lay-out provided in Annex 1 of this Order. The concerned CENROs or Implementing PENROs, and Regional Office in case of NCR, shall ensure that the storage facilities are installed with functional CCTV cameras for security purposes. The estimated establishment cost and standard material to be used for the construction of the storage facilities is provided under Annex 2 of this Order.

III. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MANAGEMENT OF STORAGE FACILITIES

The CENROs or Implementing PENROs, or Regional Office, in the case of NCR, shall oversee the management and security of storage facilities and designate at least one (1) personnel who is holding a permanent/plantilla position capable of performing the following duties and responsibilities relevant to the operation, maintenance and management of the storage facilities:

- a) Oversee the daily operations and maintenance of storage facilities;
- b) Conduct inventory of items and evaluate the status of storage facilities; and
- c) Submit a report regarding the status of storage facilities and inventory of items to the CENROs or Implementing PENROs or Enforcement Division Chief in the case of NCR.

IV. MONITORING AND REPORTING

The CENROs or Implementing PENROs, or Enforcement Division in the case of NCR, shall prepare a report using the standard prescribed reporting format provided under Annex 3 of this Order, to the concerned Regional Office, copy furnished the PENRO, PENRO Accountant and the PENRO Auditor, containing the following information:

1. Completion of Construction Report - contains a description of the storage facilities constructed, including the location and date of construction among others, to be submitted thirty (30) calendar days upon completion of the storage facilities.
2. Quarterly status report of storage facilities – provides a summary of the items currently stored in the storage facilities, including the condition of the storage facilities.
3. Quarterly inventory of items – a complete list of all turned-over logs from TCPs seized and/or confiscated illegal forest products, and the machinery,

equipment, tools, implements, and conveyances stored in the storage facility, with description of each item, date of seizure and/or confiscation, current condition, estimated market value of the items, date of disposition and mode of disposition.

The Regional Offices shall use the Electronic Filing and Monitoring System (e-FMS) for illegal logging cases as the repository of reports on apprehension, seizure and confiscation of undocumented forest products, including the machinery, equipment, tools, implements, and conveyances used in connection therewith. The Regional Offices shall also maintain an online database on the storage facilities, using the prescribed electronic spreadsheet format provided under Annex 4 of this Order. The online database shall be a consolidation of the completion of construction report, operational report on the quarterly status report and quarterly inventory of items report submitted by the CENROs or Implementing PENROs, or Enforcement Division in the case of NCR to the Regional Office. Finally, the Regional Office shall submit an annual report regarding the storage facilities in the succeeding month of the following year, using the format provided under Annex 5 of this Order, to the Office of the Undersecretary for Field Operations, copy furnished to the Director of the Forest Management Bureau.

V. FUNDING

The CENROs and Implementing PENROs, or Regional Office, in case of NCR, shall allocate funds for the construction of the storage facilities. The amount allocated for the construction of the storage facilities shall be reviewed and adjusted every five years or as deemed necessary due to extraordinary circumstances.

Further, concerned offices shall allocate sufficient amount from their respective annual budget for the management and maintenance of the constructed storage facilities as deemed necessary; provided that the concerned Office shall submit a detailed report on the status of the storage facilities indicating the need for maintenance to the Office of the Undersecretary for Field Operations copy furnished the Forest Management Bureau.

This Order shall take effect immediately.

MARIA ANTONIA YULO LOYZAGA
Secretary

Annex 2. Detailed Costs and Standard Material for the Storage Facilities

PROJECT: PROPOSED TYPICAL LOG STORAGE BUILDING					
SUBJECT: BILL OF MATERIALS AND COST ESTIMATES					
DATE: As of April 24, 2023					
ITEM	DESCRIPTION	QTY	UNIT	UNIT COST	AMOUNT (PHP)
I.	Concreting Works (Columns, Walls, Foundations, Slabs)				
	6" CHB	2960	pcs	20.00	59,200.00
	Cement	619	bags	250.00	154,750.00
	Sand	47	cu.m	1,500.00	70,500.00
	Gravel	25	cu.m	2,100.00	52,500.00
	10mm Rebar (6m)	564	pcs	150.00	87,600.00
	16mm Rebar (6m)	190	pcs	310.00	58,900.00
	GI Tie Wires #16	49	kg	85.00	4,165.00
	Paint Works (materials)	474	sq.m	80.00	37,920.00
	Epoxy Floor Coating	160	sq.m	180.00	28,800.00
	Form Works (materials)	1	lot	25,000.00	25,000.00
	Sub-total				579,335.00
II	Steel Works (Roofing)				
	2" x 2" x 3/16" Angle Bar (6m)	79	pcs	1,200.00	94,800.00
	1.5" x 1.5" x 3/16" Angle Bar (6m)	89	pcs	620.00	55,180.00
	Steel Plate (3/16")	6	sq.m	2,100.00	12,600.00
	2" x 3" x 2mm C-Purlin (6m)	77	pcs	500.00	38,500.00
	Tekscrews	1520	pcs	2.00	3,040.00
	Rib-type Long Span (Colored), G-24 (0.6mm thick)	192	sq.m	650.00	124,800.00
	Insulation Foam Double Sided (10mm thick)	192	sq.m	115.00	22,080.00
	Pre-painted Ridge Roll (8')	10	pcs	150.00	1,500.00
	Consumables (weld rods, etc.)	1	lot	15,000.00	15,000.00
	Sub-total				367,500.00
III	Electrical				
	Outlet (2 gang universal)	10	pcs	110.00	1,100.00
	Industrial Ceiling Fan	3	pcs	5,500.00	16,500.00
	General Electrical (Wiring, Breakers, Panels, Lights, etc.)	1	lot	30,000.00	30,000.00
	Consumables	1	lot	15,000.00	15,000.00
	Sub-total				62,600.00
IV	Finishing (Labor and Materials)				
	Motorized Type Roll Up Door	2	sets	58,805.00	117,610.00
	Awning Type Steel Casement Window (1m x 2m)	16	sets	1,920.00	30,720.00
	Door and Window Consumables	1	lot	10,000.00	10,000.00
	Sub-total				158,330.00
V	Summary				
	Total Materials Cost				1,167,765.00
	Labor Cost (30%)				350,329.50
	Excavation Works	35	cu.m	400.00	14,000.00
	Total Direct Cost				1,532,094.50
	Overhead, Contingencies, and Miscellaneous				153,249.45
	Contractor's Profit				99,970.34
	Total Indirect Cost				253,219.79
	VAT (12%+8C and 1C)				214,285.71
	TOTAL PROJECT COST				2,000,000.00

**Annex 3. Format of Reporting for the Status Report of Storage Facilities and Inventory of Items to be submitted by
CENRO or Implementing PENROs, or Enforcement Division in case of NCR to the Regional Office**

**DENR CENRO/Implementing PENRO (Name of Office)
(Office Address)**

Table 1. Completion of Construction Report

Name of Office	Location of Storage Facility (Barangay, Municipality, Province)	Date of Construction (Month, Day, Year)	Storage Facility Code
CENRO Dupax	Inaban, Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	September 1, 2023	PSGC

Table 2. Quarterly Status Report of Storage Facilities

Storage Facility Code (SFC)	Total Volume of Seized Products (bd. ft)	Total Volume of Forest Products Stored (bd. ft)	Total Volume of Confiscated Forest Products Stored (bd. ft)	Total No. of Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyances Stored (no)	Total No. of Confiscated Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyances Stored (no)	Total Market Value of Items (Php)	Status of Facility (serviceable/non-serviceable)
PSGC	20	10	10	2	5	1,500,000	serviceable
Grand Total							

Press Esc to exit full screen

Table 3. Quarterly Inventory of Items Stored in the Storage Facility (SFC)

Item No. (Site record-xx)	Item (Log/Lumber, Charcoal, Chainsaw, etc)	Location of Apprehension (Barangay, Municipality, Province)	Date Stored in the Facility	Type of Items (FP, METI)	Status of Items (Seized, Confiscate d)	Volume of Forest Products Stored (bd. ft.)	No. of Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyance Stored (no)	Market Value of Items	Date of Disposition	Mode of Disposition (Donation, Auction, Others)
1002023-01	Logs	Inaban, Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	October 1, 2023	FP	Confiscated	20	-	3,000,000.00	December 1, 2023	Donation
1002023-02	Charcoal	Belansa, Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	October 5, 2023	FP	Seized	25	-	30,000.00	December 1, 2023	Donation
01202024-03	Chainsaw	Inaban, Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	January 20, 2024	METI	Seized		2	50,000.00	March 1, 2024	Auction
Grand Total										

Prepared by:

Reviewed by:

Approved by:

Enforcement Section/Unit Personnel

Chief, Enforcement Section/Unit

CENRO/Implementing PENRO

Annex 4. Format of Online Database to be maintained by the Regional Office

DENR Regional Office (Name of Office)
(Office Address)

Table 1. Status Report of Storage Facilities within Region

Region	PENRO	CENRO	Location of Storage Facility (Barangay, Municipality, Province)	Date of Construction (Month, Day, Year)	Total Volume of Seized Forest Products Stored (bd, ft)	Total Volume of Confiscated Forest Products Stored (bd, ft)	Total No. of Seized Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyance Stored (no)	Total No. of Confiscated Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyance Stored (no)	Total Market Value of Items (Php)	Status of Storage Facility (serviceable/non-serviceable)
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	Inaban, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	September 1, 2023	20	10	2	5	3,000,000.00	Serviceable
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	Belenso, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya							
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	Inaban, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya							
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Arliao	Barangayan, Arliao, Nueva Vizcaya							
Grand Total										

Table 2. Inventory of Items stored in the Storage Facilities within DENR Region

Region	PENR	CENRO	Item No. (Date Store d-xxx)	Item (Logs/ Lumber, Charcoal, Chainsaw, etc)	Location of Apprehensi on (Barangay, Municipality, Province)	Date Stored in the Facility	Type of Items (FP, METI)	Status of Items Stored (Seized, Confisca ted)	Volume of Forest Products Stored (bd, Ft.)	No of Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyance Stored (no)	Market Value of Items (Php)	Date of Dispositi on	Mode of Dispositi on (Donatio n, Auction, Others)
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	100120	Logs	Inaban, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	October 1, 2023	FP	Confiscate d	20	-	3,000,000.00	December 1, 2023	Donator
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	100520	Charcoal	Belenso, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	October 5, 2023	FP	Seized	.25	-	30,000.00	December 1, 2023	Donator
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupar	012020	Chainsaw	Inaban, Dupar del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	January 20, 2024	METI	Seized		2	50,000.00	March 1, 2024	Auction
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Arliao	021520	Chainsaw	Barangayan, Arliao, Nueva Vizcaya	February 15, 2024	METI	Confiscate d		3	75,000.00		
Grand Total													

Annex 5. Format of Reporting for the Status of Storage Facilities to be submitted annually by the Regional Office to the OUF0, cc FMB

DENR Regional Office (Name of Office)
(Office Address)

Table 1. Status Report of Storage Facilities constructed within DENR Region _

Region	PENRO	CENRO	Location of Storage Facility (Barangay, Municipality, Province)	Date of Construction (Month, Day, Year)	Total Volume of Seized Forest Products Stored (bd. ft)	Total Volume of Confiscated Forest Products Stored (bd. ft)	Total No. of Seized Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyances Stored (no)	Total No. of Confiscated Machinery, Equipment, tools and conveyances Stored (no)	Status of Storage Facility (serviceable/ non-serviceable)
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Dupax	Inaban, Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya	September 1, 2023	.25	20	2	-	Serviceable
II	Nueva Vizcaya	CENRO Antao	Banganan, Antao, Nueva Vizcaya	September 24, 2023	-	-	-	3	Serviceable
Grand Total									-

Prepared by:

Chief, Enforcement Division

Approved by:

Regional Executive Director

ANNEX H
DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Environment and Natural Resources
Visayas Avenue, Diliman, 1100 Quezon City
Tel. Nos. 929-6626 to 29; 929-6633 to 35
929-7041 to 43; 929-6252; 929-1669
Website: <http://www.denr.gov.ph> E-mail: web@denrgov.ph

JUL 18 2018

DENR Administrative Order
No. 2018- 16

SUBJECT : GUIDELINES IN THE PROCESSING AND ISSUANCE OF PERMITS ON THE REMOVAL AND RELOCATION OF TREES AFFECTED BY DPWH PROJECTS

Pursuant to the Presidential Decree 705 as amended, Presidential Decree No. 953, Executive Order No. 23 S. 2011, Executive Order No. 26 S. 2011, other relevant laws, rules and regulations, and in order to fast track the processing and issuance of permits on the removal or relocation of trees affected by infrastructure projects of the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), the following guidelines are hereby prescribed for compliance of all concerned.

Section 1. Scope and Coverage

This Order shall cover all applications for removal and relocation of trees for the construction of roads, bridges, flood control and other infrastructure duly certified as government projects of the DPWH.

Section 2. Application Requirements

The following requirements shall be submitted by the DPWH to the CENRO with jurisdiction over the projects, to wit:

1. Appropriate infrastructure plan with tree charting (e.g. Road Alignment Plan, Building Plan) indicating the geotagged location of individual trees affected by the project, to be numbered sequentially, and shall be vetted by the DPWH as basis of validation by the DENR during actual cutting operations;
2. Appropriate Environmental Clearance (CNC/ECC);
3. Endorsement from the concerned Local Government Units;
4. Waiver/Consent corresponding to appropriate infrastructure plan in the case of tree cutting within private lands; and
5. Appropriate Land Tenure Instruments (LTIs) for tree cutting within forestlands.

Section 3. Guidelines in Tree Removal and Relocation.

- 3.1 Evaluation of the complete requirements shall be done upon receipt thereof. Application with incomplete requirements shall not be acted upon and returned to the applicant immediately.

The concerned CENR Office shall issue the corresponding Tree Cutting Permit and/or Earth-balling Permit (TCP/EP) within three (3) working days indicating the number of trees based on the analysis of the appropriate infrastructure plan with tree charting or if necessary, on the result of actual ocular inspection.

The CENR Office may conduct ocular inspection to verify the correctness of the submitted requirements in coordination with the DPWH before issuance of the TCP/EP on the third day as may be warranted.

- 3.2 Determination of the number of trees, location and its species nomenclature/common name, classification if naturally grown or planted, and corresponding volume shall be verified and determined upon the conduct of geotagging and tree scaling by CENRO concerned during the actual tree cutting activities. These shall serve as basis for determining the tree replacement and schedule of hauling logs and to the concerned DENR office, computation of forest charges, among others.
- 3.3 Tree removal and relocation operations, including turnover and transport of logs, shall only be done under the presence and close supervision of the DENR. Correspondingly, the DPWH shall shoulder all operational costs.

Section 4. Other Considerations. The following shall be considered in the processing and issuance of tree removal and relocation permits:

- 4.1 In case of tree removal and relocation in public forestlands, TCP/EP applications shall only be processed upon issuance of appropriate LTI secured by the DPWH from the concerned Regional Directors, subject to existing regulations.
- 4.2 To further facilitate issuance of TCP/EPs, concerned DENR Office are required to attend consultation meetings during pre-project activities of the DPWH.
- 4.3 The design of the road projects should always consider the least number of trees to be affected.

Section 5. Transitory provisions. All existing regulations in earth-balling and tree replacement shall remain in force and executory.

Section 6. Repealing Clause. All circulars, orders, memoranda, and issuances inconsistent herewith shall be amended or repealed accordingly.

Section 7. Effectivity Clause. This Order shall take effect fifteen (15) days after publication in at least two (2) newspapers of general circulation and upon submission of three (3) copies thereof to the Office of the National Administration Registrar (ONAR) from the UP Law Center.

ROY A. CIMATU
Secretary

PUBLICATION: The Manila Times
August 13, 2018
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: UP Law Center
August 20, 2018

ANNEX I
DENR Administrative Order No. 2020-06

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Environment and Natural Resources
Visayas Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City
Website: <http://www.denr.gov.ph> / E-mail: web@denrgov.ph

FEB 12 2020

DENR Administrative Order
No. 2020- 06

SUBJECT : AMENDING CERTAIN PROVISIONS AND EXPANDING THE COVERAGE OF DENR ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER NO. 2018-16 OR THE "GUIDELINES IN THE PROCESSING AND ISSUANCE OF PERMITS ON THE REMOVAL AND RELOCATION OF TREES AFFECTED BY DPWH PROJECTS"

Pursuant to the Presidential Decree No. 705 as amended, Presidential Decree No. 953, Executive Order No. 23 Series of 2011, Republic Act No. 7161, other relevant laws, rules and regulations, and in order to fast track the processing and issuance of permits on the tree cutting and/or earth-balling affected by priority infrastructure projects of National Government Agencies, the following guidelines are hereby prescribed for compliance of all concerned.

Section 1. Expanding the Scope and Coverage of DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16

The scope and coverage are hereby expanded to include all applications for the cutting and/or earth-balling of trees for the construction of roads, bridges, flood control and other infrastructure projects for public purposes of National Government Agencies (NGA) provided that the Head of NGA shall submit to DENR the annual list of priority projects.

National Government Agencies shall include DPWH, DOTr, DepEd, DA, DOH, CHED, DOE, and NIA.

Sec. 2. Section 2 of DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16 shall be amended as follows:

"Section 2. Application Requirements. The following requirements shall be submitted by the concerned National Government Agency to the CENRO with jurisdiction over the projects, to wit:

Item 1. Final and Approved Infrastructure Development Plan with tree charting (e.g. Road Alignment Plan, Building Plan, Detailed Engineering Design, or similar plan) indicating the geotagged location of individual trees affected by the project, to be numbered sequentially, as basis of validation by the DENR during actual cutting operations.

Item 5. The application for Tree Cutting and/or Earth-Balling Permits may be processed and issued even without an approved tenurial instrument.

Item 6. Certified True Copy of Clearance/Resolution from Protected Area Management Board (PAMB). The PAMB Clearance shall include an endorsement

for the EMB Regional Office to determine whether the development project or activity is eligible for a Certificate of Non-Coverage (CNC) or should undergo the scoping process under the EIS System.

A development project or activity determined by the scoping process to be environmentally critical, shall undertake a full-blown EIA. A project or activity that is found to be environmentally critical will undertake an IEE instead of EIA. In both cases, an ECC shall be required prior to the commencement of the project or activity (Section 12, Rule 12.2 of the e-NIPAS and its IRR)."

Item 7. Clearance from Palawan Council for Sustainable Development (PCSD), and Philippine Coconut Authority (PCA) among others as may be applicable."

Sec. 3. Separability Clause. Should any provision or part of this Order be declared unconstitutional, those not affected shall remain to be in force and full effect.

Sec. 4. Repealing Clause. All other provisions of DENR Administrative Order No. 2018-16 shall remain in force and executory. All circulars, orders, memoranda, and issuances inconsistent herewith shall be amended or repealed accordingly.

Sec 5. Effectivity Clause. This Order shall take effect fifteen (15) days after publication in a newspaper of general circulation and upon submission to the Office of the National Administration Registrar (ONAR) from the UP Law Center.

ROY A. CIMATU
Secretary

Malaya – Mar. 4, 2020